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Abstract

The application of Machine Learning (ML) to bridge Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) is constrained by a lack of diverse and labelled datasets. Obtaining high-quality training data from operational infrastructure is inherently difficult because critical assets are typically repaired immediately upon the detection of defects, preventing the collection of data describing diverse failure modes. To address this scarcity and enable the prototyping of robust algorithms, this study presents a framework for generating synthetic modal frequencies using a calibrated Finite Element (FE) model of the S101 bridge. Aleatory uncertainties and environmental variability are incorporated through the stochastic variation of material properties and thermal loads derived from a 20-year climate record. Analysis of the generated dataset revealed that simulated thermal loads induced frequency shifts that often exceeded those caused by minor structural damage, confirming the necessity of training on environmentally representative data. The primary

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contribution of this work is an open-access, FAIR-compliant (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) synthetic dataset, intended to serve as a standardised benchmark for the SHM research community under conditions of combined structural and environmental uncertainty. To demonstrate the utility of the generated data, the performance of a supervised multi-layer perceptron and an unsupervised k-means clustering algorithm are evaluated, with the supervised approach achieving a maximum classification accuracy of 1.00. However, the framework also reveals a fundamental modelling limitation: the linear FE approach failed to replicate the physical response under pier settlement, producing frequency shifts an order of magnitude below those observed experimentally.

Keywords: Machine Learning, S101 Bridge, Thermal Masking, Digital Twin, Finite Element Modelling, Structural Health Monitoring, Anomaly Identification

1. Introduction

The long-term structural reliability of transport infrastructure is increasingly challenged by the degradation of ageing assets, environmental exposure and rising operational demands (1). Traditional maintenance strategies have predominantly relied on visual inspections, yet these methods are labour-intensive, subjective and often limited to detecting surface-level defects in accessible areas (2). To overcome these limitations and ensure safety, Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) has transitioned towards continuous, global monitoring systems. Vibration-based methods, which depend on the principle that changes in physical properties (specifically stiffness and mass) man-

ifest as detectable shifts in modal parameters (natural frequencies, mode shapes and damping ratios), have become a cornerstone of this approach (3; 4; 5).

Recent advancements in Machine Learning (ML) have offered new opportunities to automate the interpretation of these complex vibration datasets, moving the field from manual data analysis to automated decision-making (6). The current state of the art can be broadly categorised into supervised and unsupervised learning approaches. Studies have demonstrated that supervised learning algorithms, such as Neural Networks (NNs), are capable of identifying non-linear patterns indicative of damage with high accuracy, provided they are trained on comprehensive datasets (7; 8; 9). Unsupervised methods, including clustering algorithms and outlier analysis, have also shown promise in identifying structural deviations (novelty detection) without requiring exhaustive prior knowledge of damage states. The interpretation of these deviations, however, often requires specialised expert judgement to disentangle genuine damage features from environmental noise, a process that necessitates careful attention to minimise false positives under operational variance (10; 11).

The widespread adoption of these data-driven techniques in civil engineering remains constrained by a critical data scarcity gap (12). Unlike in other domains such as computer vision, obtaining large, labelled datasets from real-world bridges in damaged states is difficult in practice. Critical infrastructure is typically repaired immediately upon the detection of significant defects to ensure public safety, preventing the collection of data describing diverse failure modes (13; 14). Therefore, most available real-world datasets

only represent the "healthy" or "reference" state of the structure, rendering high-performance ML classifiers ineffective for practical deployment.

Compounding the issue of data scarcity is the influence of environmental and operational variability. It is well-established in the literature that fluctuations in ambient temperature can induce shifts in natural frequencies that may mask or even exceed the shifts caused by structural damage (15; 16; 17; 18). Temperature typically causes a more pronounced effect than that of wind and precipitation (19; 20). As a result, algorithms trained on limited data often struggle to distinguish between benign environmental changes and genuine structural deterioration, particularly as there is no agreed-upon relationship between temperature and modal frequency response (21; 22). Training on temperature-variant datasets improves the distinction between damage and environmental effects (23), with methods such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) having also demonstrated success in separating thermal variation from genuine structural change (24). Generating synthetic data with applied thermal loads is therefore vital for robust algorithm training.

Physics-based frameworks utilising modal analysis provide a robust means of generating diverse damage scenarios grounded in structural mechanics (25), with representative numerical models identified as a necessity to overcome the practical impossibility of emulating damage on operational assets to obtain diverse training data (7). By calibrating numerical models against empirical benchmarks, such as the destructive testing campaign of the S101 post-tensioned concrete bridge by Siringoringo et al. (26), it is possible to simulate a vast array of damage scenarios that are unfeasible to capture

in the field. However, it is noted that physics-based models often rely on simplified assumptions, such as linear elastic behaviour of materials, which lack the variability inherent in real-world structures or fail to adequately integrate long-term climatic patterns (27). Furthermore, despite the existence of feature extraction benchmarks (28), there is a distinct absence of open-access, FAIR-compliant (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) datasets that allow for the rigorous benchmarking of ML algorithms under conditions of combined damage and environmental uncertainty (13; 29). Whilst recent standardisation efforts, such as BS EN 18162:2026 (30), have begun to formalise the concept of digital twins in the built environment, the practical implementation of such frameworks for SHM remains constrained by the absence of representative datasets that capture realistic damage and environmental conditions.

In summary, bridge infrastructure faces mounting safety challenges, as evidenced both by the empirical record of structural failures (31) and by the escalating threats of climate change, whose short-term hazards such as flooding and scour interact with long-term stressors such as corrosion and thermal degradation to compromise bridge safety at scale (32). These pressures have intensified the demand for robust Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) and damage detection frameworks capable of supporting proactive asset management. Physics-enhanced machine learning and digital twinning have emerged as particularly promising paradigms in this regard (33). However, a critical bottleneck remains: real-world monitoring data is expensive to acquire, limited in volume, and rarely captures the full spectrum of damage states relevant for algorithm development.

The present paper addresses this gap, proposing a FAIR-compliant synthetic data generation methodology specifically tailored to the prototyping of bridge damage detection algorithms, thereby advancing the field towards more generalisable and practically deployable SHM solutions. This is achieved through the simultaneous integration of three sources of variability absent from prior work on this structure: stochastic aleatory uncertainty in material properties and boundary conditions, long-term thermal loading derived from a 20-year historical climate record (34) and a range of representative structural damage scenarios. Furthermore, a quantified demonstration of thermal masking effects across multiple damage typologies and severities is conducted, providing direct evidence to inform the design of environmentally compensated ML classifiers. To demonstrate the utility of the generated data, the performance of a supervised NN (multi-layer perceptron) (7) and an unsupervised k-means clustering algorithm (10) are evaluated to assess the suitability of the synthetic database for classifying damage states amidst simulated environmental noise.

2. Methodology

This study employs a physics-based framework to generate a comprehensive synthetic dataset suitable for training ML algorithms. The methodology leverages a calibrated FE model of the S101 bridge to simulate the structure’s dynamic response under diverse conditions, comprising stochastic aleatory uncertainties, realistic thermal loads and distinct damage scenarios. The resulting dataset was subsequently used to train and evaluate the performance of both supervised and unsupervised ML classifiers.

2.1. Finite Element Model Setup and Uncertainty Simulation

The synthetic data generation utilised a calibrated FE model of the S101 bridge developed using Ansys, as detailed by Jiménez Rios et al. (35). This model serves as the baseline for the undamaged condition, having been calibrated against empirical data from progressive damage testing (26) to ensure physical fidelity.

To produce a representative dataset that accounts for real-world variability, aleatory uncertainties were introduced into the model. Since the baseline model accounted for epistemic uncertainties during the calibration process, this study focused on the stochastic variation of material properties and boundary conditions to mimic operational and construction variances. The Young's modulus of all concrete components, including the deck and piers, was treated as a random variable following a normal distribution. The mean of this distribution was set to the calibrated nominal value, with a coefficient of variation of 2%, justified as follows. The elastic modulus of concrete varies with compressive strength raised to the power of one third (BS EN 1992-1-1:2023 §5.1.4 (36)). Applying a first-order Taylor series expansion, the coefficient of variation of Young's modulus is approximately one third of that of compressive strength. Given the within-member compressive strength coefficient of variation of around 7% reported by Bartlett and MacGregor (37), this yields a corresponding coefficient of variation for Young's modulus of approximately 2%. Additionally, the stiffnesses of the foundation springs at the abutments were varied using the same normal distribution parameters. This approach ensured that the model captured the inherent randomness of soil-structure interaction.

A total of 365 independent realisations of the undamaged bridge were generated under both thermally loaded and non-thermal conditions, yielding two sets of 365 simulations for the baseline state. This number was chosen to correspond directly to the days of a calendar year, enabling a one-to-one mapping of historical daily mean temperature records to individual model iterations and ensuring a balanced sample size across simulation sets. Each realisation underwent a modal analysis to extract the first six natural frequencies, exceeding the four modes identified during the original S101 experimental campaign by Siringoringo et al. (26) and the five modes considered in the associated conference paper by Jiménez Rios et al. (35). This encompasses the full set of experimentally characterised modes whilst providing additional higher-mode information to enrich the dataset.

2.2. Simulation of Damage Scenarios

The same simulation procedure was then applied to three distinct damage cases, each representing a realistic deterioration mechanism observed in ageing infrastructure. For each severity within all three damage cases, two equivalent sets of 365 thermally loaded and non-thermal realisations were generated. The damage scenarios were selected to broadly reflect the controlled pre-demolition testing campaign conducted on the S101 bridge (26), particularly pier weakening, and are summarised in Table 1.

2.2.1. Stiffness Reduction (Cases 1 & 2)

Damage Cases 1 and 2 simulated material degradation, such as cracking or corrosion-induced internal voiding, through localised stiffness reductions (7). These were implemented by reducing the Young's modulus of the affected

Table 1: Defined damage cases and severities applied to the FE model (components depicted in Figure 1)

Damage Case	Mechanism	Model Component	Severities
Case 1	Pier Stiffness Reduction	Concrete Columns	10%, 20%, 40%
Case 2	Mid-Deck Stiffness Reduction	Concrete CD	10%, 20%, 40%
Case 3	Pier Settlement	Concrete Columns	3 cm, 5 cm, 10 cm

component by 10%, 20% and 40%: a single *Concrete Columns* component (one pier) for Case 1 and a single *Concrete CD* component (one mid-span deck section) for Case 2 (Figure 1). To maintain consistency with the uncertainty modelling, the reduced stiffness values served as the new mean for the normal distribution, ensuring that stochastic variability remained present even within the damaged regions.

2.2.2. Pier Settlement (Case 3)

Case 3 simulated geometric deformation due to differential foundation settlement. Consistent with the experimental campaign on the S101 bridge (26), this was modelled by applying controlled vertical displacements of 3 cm, 5 cm and 10 cm to the base of a single *Concrete Columns* component (Figure

1). Boundary conditions were modified to permit vertical displacement while maintaining horizontal restraint.

Figure 1: Calibrated FE model of the S101 bridge discretised by material component (the bridge deck spans 58 m in total length, with a main span of 32 m, adjacent spans of 12 m between centres and a width of 7.2 m (35))

2.3. Incorporation of Thermal Effects

To capture the influence of temperature fluctuations on modal frequencies, a steady-state thermal analysis was integrated into the simulation workflow. A dataset of 365 daily mean temperatures was compiled from a 20-year historical climate record for a nearby Austrian weather station (34), representing a full annual cycle, and applied uniformly to the structural model prior to each modal analysis. All undamaged and damaged simulations were run under these thermal loading conditions. A corresponding set of non-thermal simulations was also produced for each case, enabling direct assessment of the extent to which temperature fluctuations mask damage-induced frequency shifts.

It is acknowledged that this uniform steady-state approach represents a simplification of the complex spatial and temporal thermal gradients present

in real structures; the implications of this assumption are discussed further in Section 3.4.

2.4. Automation and Data Handling

The generation of 7,300 total model iterations (comprising 365 simulations across 20 distinct structural states) necessitated a fully automated workflow. Python scripts were deployed within Ansys Workbench to iteratively assign stochastic material properties and boundary conditions based on a defined random seed, ensuring reproducibility. A secondary script within Ansys Mechanical managed the sequential execution of the steady-state thermal, static structural and modal analyses. The first six natural frequencies were extracted for each iteration and exported to CSV format.

Post-processing involved restructuring the simulation outputs into labelled datasets, with 0 and 1 denoting the undamaged and damaged states respectively, suitable for use in supervised learning. The datasets were compiled in accordance with FAIR principles (29) and are openly accessible via an online repository (38) to support future benchmarking and algorithm development.

2.5. Machine Learning Algorithm Development

Two distinct ML algorithms were developed to assess the suitability of the synthetically generated data for classifying the bridge's condition from modal frequency outputs: a supervised multi-layer perceptron NN and an unsupervised k-means clustering algorithm. For both algorithms, the dataset was partitioned into 70% training and 30% testing sets. A fixed random state was also applied to both algorithms to ensure the reproducibility of results.

2.5.1. Supervised Neural Network

A multi-layer perceptron classifier was implemented using the scikit-learn library. The architecture comprised an input layer of six neurons (corresponding to the first six natural frequencies), followed by four dense hidden layers containing 100, 50, 30 and 15 neurons, respectively. The ReLU activation function was applied to introduce non-linearity.

The model was optimised using the L-BFGS solver, with an alpha regularisation parameter of $1e-3$ to mitigate overfitting, and trained for up to 1,000 iterations. Performance was evaluated using accuracy, the confusion matrix and the Area Under the Curve (AUC) of the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC).

2.5.2. Unsupervised K-Means Clustering

To assess damage detection capabilities without labelled training data, a k-means clustering algorithm was employed. The algorithm partitioned the modal frequency data into two clusters (representing damaged and undamaged states) by minimising the distance to cluster centroids. The model was executed with 500 random initialisations and up to 1,000 iterations to ensure stability. Performance was assessed using the Rand Index (RI), and PCA was utilised to reduce the dimensionality of data in order to visualise the separation of clusters in two-dimensional space.

3. Results and Discussion

This section presents the statistical distributions of the synthetically generated modal frequency data, evaluates the classification performance of the two ML algorithms and discusses the physical interpretation of the findings.

The complete dataset (38) comprises 7,300 model iterations, spanning 20 distinct structural states under varying thermal conditions, yielding 43,800 individual frequency datapoints in total.

Each set of model iterations comprises the first six natural frequencies of the bridge, corresponding to the mode shapes depicted in Figure 2. These encompass a mix of bending, torsional and lateral modes.

Figure 2: First six mode shapes of the S101 bridge calibrated numerical model (not to scale)

3.1. Influence of Environmental Variability

The application of thermal loads, derived from the 20-year historical climate record (34), produced a consistent reduction in mean natural frequencies across all modes relative to the non-thermal baseline. As illustrated in Figure 3, mean frequency shifts ranged from -0.13% to -1.33% across the six modes, with the largest shift observed in Mode 1 and the smallest in Mode 3. The interquartile range of the frequency distributions also increased no-

tably under thermal loading, reflecting the additional variability introduced by seasonal temperature fluctuations. Scatter plots, illustrated in Figure 4, confirmed a negative translation of frequencies, particularly during simulated summer months, demonstrating the pronounced sensitivity of the bridge's dynamic response to ambient environmental conditions.

These findings suggest that environmental variability poses a significant challenge to vibration-based SHM. Temperature-induced frequency shifts of up to -1.33% often exceeded those caused by minor structural damage, as demonstrated in the damage scenario analysis that follows. This appears consistent with observations by Figueiredo et al. (17) and Wang et al. (15), who noted that thermal effects can mask damage signals in operational structures. Consequently, the necessity of training algorithms on datasets that explicitly incorporate environmental variability is reinforced, as models trained solely on non-thermal data risk generating false positives under operational conditions (16).

Figure 3: Box plots of natural frequency distributions for the undamaged case with and without thermal loads

Figure 4: Scatter diagrams of natural frequency distributions for the undamaged case with and without thermal loads

3.2. Analysis of Damage Scenarios

3.2.1. Pier Stiffness Reduction (Case 1)

Simulated pier stiffness reductions produced detectable downward shifts in natural frequencies (Figure 6), the magnitude of which correlated consistently with damage severity. A 40% reduction in pier stiffness under thermal loads resulted in mean frequency shifts ranging from -0.51% to -1.27% across the six modes, with the largest shift observed in Mode 1 and the smallest in Mode 2 (Figure 5). Modes 1, 4 and 6 exhibited the greatest sensitivity. Mode 2 showed comparatively lower sensitivity at -0.51%, indicating limited modal participation from the affected pier. At lower severities, a 10% stiffness reduction produced shifts of approximately -0.36% for Mode 1, which resulted in substantial overlap between the damaged and undamaged frequency distributions once thermal variability was superimposed.

This overlap at low damage severities is particularly significant. The thermally induced mean frequency shift of -1.33% in Mode 1 exceeds the damage-induced shift of -0.36% at 10% pier stiffness reduction by a ratio of approximately 3.7, rendering the two states statistically indistinguishable without prior knowledge of the thermal contribution. This behaviour illustrates precisely the challenge that motivated the inclusion of environmental variability in the synthetic framework and shows why algorithms trained on non-thermal data are likely to underperform in operation. ML models trained on non-thermal data achieved perfect accuracy (1.00) for severe damage but saw performance drop markedly when thermal loads were introduced, as discussed further in Section 3.3.

Figure 5: Box plots of natural frequency distributions for the undamaged and 40% pier stiffness reduction cases, both under thermal loads

Figure 6: Scatter diagrams of natural frequency distributions for the undamaged and 40% pier stiffness reduction cases, both under thermal loads

3.2.2. Mid-Deck Stiffness Reduction (Case 2)

Mid-deck stiffness reduction produced the most pronounced frequency deviations of all simulated damage cases. Under thermal loads, a 40% re-

duction in deck stiffness caused mean frequency shifts ranging from -0.24% to -3.35% across the six modes, with the largest shift observed in Mode 1 and the smallest in Mode 6 (Figure 7). Also notable was a -2.17% shift in Mode 5; these shifts were of sufficient magnitude to remain distinguishable from thermal noise across all tested severities. Mode 6, by contrast, exhibited negligible sensitivity at -0.24%, reflecting minimal participation of the mid-span section in that mode shape. Comparing the thermal and non-thermal simulations for this damage case, the addition of thermal loads induced supplementary mean frequency shifts ranging from -0.15% (Mode 3) to -1.53% (Mode 1) compared to the non-thermal simulation. Notably, the thermally induced shift in Mode 1 approached the magnitude of the damage-induced shift itself, resulting in a visible downward translation of the entire frequency distribution (Figure 8). Despite this superimposed environmental variability, the separation between the damaged and undamaged distributions remained sufficient for reliable classification at 40% severity, as reflected in the NN accuracy of 0.99 under thermal loading, discussed further in Section 3.3.

The strong detectability of mid-deck damage across all severities, even under thermal loading, is attributable to the location and extent of the stiffness reduction. The mid-span region contributes substantially to the global bending and torsional modes of the deck, such that even a 10% reduction produces frequency shifts (-1.09% in Mode 1) that, whilst partially masked by temperature, retain sufficient separation from the undamaged distribution for the NN to classify reliably (0.93 accuracy). This contrasts distinctly with the pier stiffness case, where the localised nature of the damage limits its influence on the global modal response.

Figure 7: Box plots of natural frequency distributions for the undamaged and 40% mid-deck stiffness reduction cases, both under thermal loads

Figure 8: Scatter diagrams of natural frequency distributions for the undamaged and 40% mid-deck stiffness reduction cases, both under thermal loads

3.2.3. Pier Settlement (Case 3)

In contrast to the stiffness reduction cases, simulated pier settlement yielded minimal frequency variations across all modes and severities. Even

at the maximum settlement of 10 cm, mean frequency shifts ranged from -0.06% to -0.71% across the six modes, with the largest shift observed in Mode 1 and the smallest in Mode 3 (Figure 9), with all remaining modes exhibiting minor change. To contextualise these shifts, the comparison between the thermal and non-thermal results of this damage case demonstrated that temperature alone accounts for mean frequency reductions of -0.13% to -1.33% across the six modes. The settlement-induced shifts are therefore of comparable or lesser magnitude to those produced by seasonal temperature variation alone, meaning that the damage signal is largely indistinguishable from normal environmental fluctuation within the thermally loaded distributions. Consequently, the damaged and undamaged frequency distributions showed considerable overlap, as is evident in Figure 10.

Table 2 presents a direct comparison between the synthetic results for a 3 cm settlement and the empirical data recorded during the S101 destructive testing campaign (26). The discrepancy is considerable; the physical experiment recorded frequency reductions of between 9.23% and 23.09%, whereas the numerical simulation produced reductions of less than 1% across all mode shapes. This order-of-magnitude difference indicates that the linear FE modelling approach, which applies geometric displacement without inducing internal stress redistribution or progressive cracking, fails to replicate the non-linear damage mechanisms present in the real structure. This limitation is consistent with observations by Karimi and Gündel (27), who noted that simplified linear models cannot adequately capture crack opening or stress redistribution under settlement loading. Future research should therefore prioritise high-fidelity non-linear modelling for this damage class, as

the current implementation produces synthetic data that is insufficiently discriminative for reliable algorithm training, as is further evidenced in Section 3.3.

Figure 9: Box plots of natural frequency distributions for the undamaged and 10 cm pier settlement cases, both under thermal loads

Figure 10: Scatter diagrams of natural frequency distributions for the undamaged and 10 cm pier settlement cases, both under thermal loads

Table 2: Comparison of natural frequency percentage change between experimental data (2.7 cm settlement / 'Damage 5') (26) and synthetic simulation (3 cm settlement).

Mode Shape	Experimental Change	Synthetic Change
1 st Bending	-9.23%	-0.60%
1 st Torsion	-17.31%	-0.48%
2 nd Bending	-15.40%	-0.12%
2 nd Torsion	-23.09%	-0.21%

3.3. Machine Learning Classification Performance

The classification results for both algorithms across all damage cases and thermal conditions are summarised in Table 3. The supervised NN consistently outperformed the unsupervised k-means algorithm across all scenarios, with the advantage being most pronounced under thermal loading and at lower damage severities. The supervised approach benefited directly from the availability of labelled synthetic data, allowing it to learn non-linear relationships between frequency shifts and damage states (7). In contrast, the unsupervised k-means algorithm relied on the geometric separation of clusters in frequency space, which became increasingly indistinct as thermal variance caused distributions to overlap.

For mid-deck stiffness reduction (Case 2), the NN achieved accuracies of 0.99 and 1.00 at 40% severity under thermal and non-thermal conditions respectively, reflecting the large and well-separated frequency shifts produced by this damage case. Performance remained strong even at 10% severity (0.93 under both thermal conditions), suggesting that deck stiffness loss is reliably detectable from modal frequency data alone. For pier stiffness reduction (Case 1), classification accuracy degraded more significantly with decreasing

severity and the introduction of thermal loads. At 10% severity, accuracy fell from 0.77 under non-thermal conditions to 0.61 under thermal loading, approaching the threshold of reliable detection. The corresponding k-means RI values of 0.55 and 0.54 confirm that the unsupervised algorithm performed little better than random assignment under these conditions.

The settlement case (Case 3) proved effectively undetectable by both algorithms under thermal loading. NN accuracies of 0.59 to 0.61 and RI values at or below 0.55 are consistent with random classification, a direct consequence of the negligible frequency shifts produced by the linear settlement model being fully masked by thermal variability. Even under non-thermal conditions, where the NN achieved 0.95 accuracy at 10 cm severity, performance at 3 cm settlement fell to 0.69, indicating that the synthetic data for this case lacks the discriminative signal necessary for reliable damage identification.

The learning curve for Case 1 at 40% severity under thermal loads is illustrated in Figure 11, revealing that whilst overfitting diminished as the training set size increased towards 730 samples, the training and validation scores had not fully converged at this dataset size. This supports the argument by Izonin et al. (39) regarding the challenges of limited datasets and indicates that the current scale of synthetic generation, whilst sufficient to demonstrate the framework's utility, would benefit from expansion to achieve a more stable and generalisable classifier. Data augmentation techniques or significantly larger synthetic generation campaigns are likely necessary to realise the full potential of the proposed framework.

Figure 11: Neural network learning curve for Damage Case 1 (40% severity, thermal load)

Table 3: Accuracy and AUC (supervised NN) and RI (unsupervised k-means) results across damage cases with and without thermal loads

Damage Case	Thermal*	Sev.	Supervised NN		Unsupervised
			Accuracy	AUC	RI
1) Pier Stiffness Reduction	N	40%	1.00	1.00	0.86
	N	20%	0.95	0.96	0.62
	N	10%	0.77	0.77	0.55
	Y	40%	0.95	0.95	0.74
	Y	20%	0.68	0.68	0.59
	Y	10%	0.61	0.61	0.54
2) Mid Deck Stiffness Reduction	N	40%	1.00	1.00	0.98
	N	20%	1.00	1.00	0.71
	N	10%	0.93	0.93	0.56
	Y	40%	0.99	0.99	0.95
	Y	20%	0.99	0.99	0.64
	Y	10%	0.93	0.93	0.55
3) Pier Settlement	N	10cm	0.95	0.95	0.55
	N	5cm	0.82	0.82	0.52
	N	3cm	0.69	0.69	0.52
	Y	10cm	0.61	0.62	0.55
	Y	5cm	0.61	0.61	0.52
	Y	3cm	0.59	0.59	0.52

* Y = with thermal loads applied; N = non-thermal.

3.4. *Modelling Limitations*

Whilst the framework demonstrated clear utility for stiffness-based damage cases, three limitations warrant consideration. First, the linear approximation of pier settlement produced synthetic data that failed to reflect the physical reality of the damage mechanism, as evidenced by the order-of-magnitude discrepancy with experimental observations. Addressing this requires the adoption of non-linear FE modelling techniques capable of simulating crack propagation and internal stress redistribution.

Second, whilst this study utilised a steady-state uniform thermal profile, real structures experience complex spatial and temporal thermal gradients across their cross-sections. Incorporating non-uniform thermal distributions derived from more detailed thermomechanical analyses could further enhance the physical fidelity of the synthetic dataset and improve the realism of the masking effect captured in training data.

Finally, validation against field monitoring data from similar operational structures remains essential to ensure that trained algorithms do not merely learn the intrinsic patterns of the synthetic generation process itself (40). A classifier that performs well on synthetic data but fails to generalise to real sensor measurements would offer limited practical value for operational SHM. Cross-validation against in-situ measurements from instrumented bridges would provide the necessary evidence that the learned frequency-damage relationships reflect genuine structural behaviour rather than artefacts of the modelling assumptions.

4. Conclusions

This study has presented a physics-based framework for generating synthetic modal frequency data from a calibrated FE model of the S101 bridge, targeting the dual objectives of addressing data scarcity in vibration-based SHM and providing an openly accessible, FAIR-compliant benchmark dataset for the research community. By integrating stochastic aleatory uncertainty, long-term thermal variability derived from a 20-year climate record and three representative structural damage cases, the framework produces a novel, physically grounded training environment that more closely reflects operational conditions than datasets generated under idealised, non-thermal assumptions.

The principal finding of this work is that environmental variability cannot be treated as a secondary consideration in the design of synthetic training datasets. Temperature-induced frequency shifts of up to -1.33% routinely exceeded the modal perturbations attributable to minor structural deterioration, rendering certain damage states statistically indistinguishable from healthy operation without explicit environmental compensation. This has a direct consequence for algorithm development: supervised classifiers trained on non-thermal data demonstrated inflated performance under controlled conditions but degraded markedly when thermal loads were introduced, confirming that environmental representativeness is a prerequisite for generalisable damage detection models.

Damage detectability was found to be strongly governed by the structural role of the affected component. Mid-deck stiffness loss produced frequency deviations sufficiently large to support reliable classification across all tested

severities, even under thermal loading, owing to the substantial contribution of the mid-span region to the global bending and torsional response of the structure. Pier stiffness reductions were detectably smaller in their modal influence and more readily obscured by thermal variance. The supervised multi-layer perceptron consistently outperformed the unsupervised k-means algorithm across all scenarios, with the advantage most pronounced where thermal noise and low damage severity caused frequency distributions to overlap, conditions under which geometric cluster separation becomes unreliable.

The linear FE modelling approach adopted here was found to be insufficient for simulating pier settlement. The order-of-magnitude discrepancy between the synthetic frequency shifts and those recorded during the S101 destructive testing campaign indicates that geometric displacement within a linear elastic framework does not reproduce the crack propagation and stress redistribution that govern the physical response under this failure mode. The settlement case therefore produced synthetic data that is insufficiently discriminative to serve as reliable training material within the current linear modelling framework. Synthetic generation of settlement scenarios is unlikely to yield useful training data until non-linear FE modelling is adopted for this damage class.

Taken together, these findings suggest that physics-based synthetic data generation, when grounded in a well-calibrated model and augmented with realistic environmental variability, offers a credible route to addressing the labelled data scarcity that currently constrains the development and benchmarking of ML-based SHM algorithms. The FAIR-compliant dataset pro-

duced in this study (38), comprising 7,300 model iterations across 20 distinct structural states, is intended to serve as a standardised reference against which future classifiers can be evaluated under conditions of combined structural and environmental uncertainty.

Future work should prioritise the adoption of non-linear FE modelling to improve the physical fidelity of settlement and cracking scenarios, incorporating material behaviours such as progressive crack opening, corrosion-induced voiding and tendon yielding in place of the simplified stiffness reductions employed within this study. Thermal modelling should similarly advance beyond uniform steady-state profiles towards spatially non-uniform gradients derived from empirical data, capturing the cross-sectional temperature differentials that influence real structural response. A further priority is the transition from binary classification towards algorithms capable of localising damage and quantifying severity. Validation against field monitoring data from operational bridges remains essential to ensure that trained models generalise beyond the patterns of the synthetic generation process itself, and the extension of the framework to additional bridge typologies would strengthen confidence in its broader applicability.

Ultimately, a validated and extensible synthetic data framework of this kind has the potential to address the labelled data scarcity that currently constrains the deployment of ML-based SHM in practice. Such a framework could enable the development of algorithms capable of detecting and localising damage in ageing infrastructure without requiring the collection of data from structures in genuinely deteriorated states, thereby supporting more proactive, evidence-based maintenance of transport networks.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Declaration of Generative AI and AI-Assisted Technologies in the Manuscript Preparation Process

In preparing this manuscript, the authors employed generative AI tools to support the structuring and linguistic polishing of text. Following the use of these tools, the authors carefully reviewed and revised the material as necessary and assume full responsibility for the final content of the published article.

Data Statement

The synthetic modal frequency dataset generated in this study, comprising 7,300 model iterations and 43,800 individual frequency datapoints across 20 structural states, is publicly available (38) in accordance with FAIR principles (29).

Author Contributions

Matvei Sinden: Conceptualisation, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Visualisation, Writing (original draft).

Alejandro Jiménez Rios: Conceptualisation, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Writing (review & editing).

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